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Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW THE PREVALENCE AND ETIOLOGY OF
ESOPHAGEAL VARICES AMONG LIVER CIRRHOSIS
PATIENTS**

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Abstract:

Objective: To determine the cause and frequency of esophageal varices in patients with liver cirrhosis **Study**

Design: A cross-sectional study.

Location and Duration: In the Gastroenterology Department of Mayo Hospital, Lahore for six months duration from September 2014 to March 2015.

Methods: The study included 200 patients with liver cirrhosis. Based on past, clinical examination and biochemical parameters, patients were classified according to the Child Pugh classification as A, B and C. Each patient was then administered an esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) for its presence and classification of esophageal varices

Results: Of the 200 patients, 79 (39.5%) were female and 121 (60.5%) were male. The mean age $\pm$ standard deviation was 46.79 ± 7.59 years and the mean $\pm$ standard deviation time of disease was 31.18 ± 29.72 months. The majority of the patients were 182 (91%) HCV +, 10% (5%) HBV +ve, 6 (3%) HCV and HBV co-infections and 2 (1%) alcoholics. In the classification of children, 89 (44.5%) were class A, 71 (35.5%) were class B and 40 (20%) were class C. There were varicose veins in 141 patients in A and varicose veins in 59 patients in B. Of the 141 varicose veins, 30 had small varicose veins, 71 had intermediate varicose veins and 40 had large varicose veins.

Conclusion: Hepatitis C is the most common cause of liver cirrhosis. Men are more affected than women. Most of the patients have A class cough and most of the patients with liver cirrhosis have middle varices.

Key words: Hepatitis C, liver cirrhosis, esophageal varices.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cirrhosis of the liver is histopathologically defined as hepatic parenchymal fibrosis. It is the final stage of a complex hepatocyte lesion process that produces liver cirrhosis, partial degeneration and hepatic fibrosis. In the past, cirrhosis of the liver is thought to be irreversible, but now, it can be reversed after the discontinuation of alcoholic cirrhosis of the alcohol, cirrhosis of the liver, the elimination of the causes of cirrhosis of the liver, reversible, and likewise the reversal of fibrosis after successful treatment of hemochromatosis. The incidence of liver disease worldwide is 5% to 10%. The incidence of cirrhosis varies from one country to another and from one region to another. In countries where alcohol consumption is more common, alcoholic cirrhosis and low alcohol consumption, hepatotropic viruses are the main cause of cirrhosis. Cirrhosis is 50.3% and non-alcoholic cirrhosis is 39.5%. Damage that leads to the activation of star cells in hepatic parenchyma also calls for secreting the transforming growth factor-B1 (TGF-B1) which leads to fibrotic response and proliferation of connective tissue myofibroblasts. The equilibrium between matrix metalloproteinase and metalloproteinase (TMP1-2) natural tissue inhibitor is changed, causing the formation of scar tissue tissue, connective tissue with the matrix and the location of the liver tissue. The presence of hepatocyte nodules in scar tissue and

regeneration prevents portal blood circulation causing portal hypertension. Complications of liver cirrhosis include HPS, portal hypertension, portosystemic collateral vessels, esophageal varices, acid, spontaneous bacterial peritonitis, hepatic encephalopathy, hepatorenal syndrome. Esophageal varices are the second cause of death in cirrhotic patients. The prevalence of esophageal varice is higher in decompensated cirrhosis patients and 60% higher than patients with compensated cirrhosis. In patients with liver cirrhosis, the prognosis of the disease can be assessed by classifying patients according to the Child Pugh classification. This study was carried out to determine the most common cause of liver cirrhosis and the prevalence of esophageal varices in Pakistan.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Gastroenterology Department of Mayo Hospital, Lahore for six months duration from September 2014 to March 2015. 200 patients with liver cirrhosis selected through convenient sampling. Regardless of the cause of liver cirrhosis, diagnosed patients were selected from 20 to 60 years of age. A detailed history was made and a clinical examination was performed according to inclusion and exclusion criteria. The patients were classified as A, B and C according to Child Pugh classification (Table 1).

Table 1: Child-Pugh score⁷

Measure	1 point	2 points	3 points	Units
Bilirubin (total)	<34 (<2)	34-50 (2-3)	>50(>3)	µmol/l (mg/dL)
Serum albumin	>35	28-35	<28	mg/L
INR	<1.7	1.71-2.20	> 2.20	no unit
Ascites	None	Suppressed with medication	Refractory	no unit
Hepatic encephalopathy	None	Grade I-II (or suppressed with medication)	Grade III-IV (or refractory)	no unit

Points	Class	Life expectancy	Mortality
5-6	A	15-20	10%
7-9	B	Candidate for transplant	30%
10-15	C	1-3 months	82%

All patients underwent upper gastrointestinal endoscopy with Gastroscope after 12 hours of midnight. Four groups

were formed in the endoscopic findings; Group I patients without varicose veins, group II with small varicose veins, moderate varicose vein group III and large varicose vein group IV (Table 2).

Table.2. Guideline for Diagnosing Esophageal Varices⁸

1. A screening esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) for the diagnosis of esophageal and gastric varices is recommended when a diagnosis of cirrhosis has been made		
2. Surveillance endoscopies are recommended on the basis of the level of cirrhosis, presence and size of the varices:		
<i>Patients with and Repeat EGD</i>		
Compensated cirrhosis	No varices	Every 2-3 years
	Small varices	Every 1-2 years
Decompensated cirrhosis	-	Yearly intervals
3. Progression of gastrointestinal varices can be determined on the basis of the size classification at the time of EGD. In practice, the recommendations for medium-sized varices in the three-size classification are the same as for large varices in the two-size classification:		
<i>Size of varix</i>	<i>Two-size classification</i>	<i>Three-size classification</i>
Small	<5 mm	Minimally elevated veins above the esophageal mucosal surface
Medium		Tortuous veins occupying less than one-third of esophageal lumen
Large	>5 mm	Occupying more than one-third of the esophageal lumen

Data were entered and analyzed with SPSS 17.0. Mean $\pm$ SD was provided for normally distributed quantitative variables. The frequencies and percentages for qualitative variables are given.

RESULTS:

200 patients with liver cirrhosis were included. There were 79 females (39.5%) and 121 males (60.5%). The mean age $\pm$ standard deviation of the patients was 46.79 ± 7.59 years. Mean $\pm$ SD duration of the disease. The patients were 31.18 ± 29.72 months. Hepatitis C was present in 182 patients with 91%. Patients with combined hepatitis B and hepatitis C were 3 to 6%. Patients with hepatitis B were 10% to 10%. Alcoholic patients were 2 to 1%. In Child Pugh class A, 89 patients (44.5%), in Child Pugh B 71 (35.5%) and in Child Pugh C (20%) were 40 patients. The patients without varicose veins were 59, but 141 patients had esophageal varices. Thirty patients had small varicose veins, 71 had varicose veins and 40 had large varicose veins.

Table.3. Baseline characteristics of the patients with liver cirrhosis (n=200)

Characteristics of patient	Liver cirrhotic pts
Male	121 (60.5%)
Female	79 (39.5%)
Age (years)	46.79±7.59
Duration of disease (months)	31.18± 29.72
Etiology	
HCV	182(91%)
HBV	10(5%)
HBV,HCV	6 (3%)
Alcoholic	2 (1%)
Child pugh class	
A	89(44.5%)
B	71(35.5%)
C	40(20%)
Esophageal varices	
No varices	59
Varices present	141
Small varices	30
Medium varices	71
Large varices	40

DISCUSSION:

The prevalence of chronic liver cirrhosis in Pakistan is increasing rapidly. It is the most common cause of morbidity and mortality. Gastrointestinal bleeding from varicose veins in cirrhotic liver patients is the most common complication causing death. The finding of this study is that HCV is the most common cause of cirrhosis of the liver is consistent with these studies and 14 million people are hepatitis C patients, Pakistan is the most common cause of cirrhosis in liver 182 patients of 200 patients studied, ie 91%. HBV showed 10 (5%) and co-infection with HBV in patients and HCV was 6 (3%), with 19 patients with alcohol only 2 (1%). The prognosis of the disease reported in many studies was that according to the Child-Pugh classification and the results were significantly longer life compared to the children in the class of patients, in this study classes B and C, the patient was a 89 (44.5%) subclass of the class B' 71 Most of the patients (35.5%) and the childpugh class 'C' were 40 (20%) were A grade A children, complying with a previous study reporting 37% of A class children. According to endoscopy, the classification of esophageal varices in patients who have been assessed for the presence or absence of varicose veins was also carried out to assess the progression of esophageal varices. Cirrhosis is the most advanced form of liver disease. Variceal bleeding is one of the most lethal complications of cirrhosis. When esophageal varices are formed, the

risk of bleeding is between 20% and 35% in 2 years. In patients with the first episode of bleeding, the mortality rate was 17% to 57%, and the first episode survived and the risk of recurrent bleeding at 66% in the first 6 months of untreated episodes. The greater the likelihood of bleeding in cirrhotic patients with large varicose veins. Preventive efforts will be attained to identify patients with large varicose veins. In 1997, American Gastroenterology Redemptio recommended endoscopic screening for patients with liver cirrhosis. In addition, the American Society for the Study of Liver Disease in 1998 suggested endoscopy screening portal hypertension (collaterals of portal veins in the abdominal image to detect class B and C, and class A varicose veins, especially when patients with large evidence of thrombocytopenia). Prophylactic treatment will reduce the incidence of bleeding and decrease the mortality rate if large varices are initiated immediately after detection. In this study, the vast majority of patients, ie, 141 of 200 patients, had varicose veins and only 59 had no varicose veins. According to the classification of varicose veins, medium-sized varicose veins, this may be due to a different sample of the population, which is the most common among all patients with small varicose veins, in 30 patients in 40 patients and in large varices in 40 patients who contradict some previous studies.

CONCLUSION:

Hepatitis C is the most common cause of cirrhosis and most of the patients have been concluded that varicose veins are mostly middle varices in children class A seen in cirrhosis patients.

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